

Tracking Course and Curriculum Progressions at the University of Virginia

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I. ABSTRACT

At UVA there is no central database to look at each major and the courses required for that major and also no way to see the paths students take in order to complete their major. We were tasked with solving each of these problems. For these tasks we created a singular file with all of the majors at UVA, and their requirements, and a way to find differences in performance and retention between majors based on sociodemographic characteristics and the class order students took to fulfill their requirements. Our method to solving this problem involved creating a way to visualize the path that students take to move through their major requirements.

II. INTRODUCTION

For this capstone project we have been working on Tracking Course and Curriculum Progression of students here at the University of Virginia. We worked with the UVA Center for Teaching Excellence (UVA CTE) on this project. We have been tasked with finding differences in performance and retention between majors based on sociodemographic characteristics. The way we were able to do this is by finding a way to visualize the path that students take to move through major requirements. Similarly, we wanted to be able to see the way that this path changes as we specify factors such as grade, socioeconomic status, or demographics. For example, part of this required making a list of each major and all the required classes to complete that major. This was to be one of our deliverables, along with a future proofed R program capable of reading in SIS data and cleaning it to be used in our path visualizations. We succeeded in creating this program, creating pathway visualizations, and engineering a centralized list of all the major requirements. Because of privacy concerns, we were only ever able to work with anonymized data and could only create a framework for the analysis requested. The UVA Center for Teaching Excellence will be able to complete the analysis using the code we provided to them.

III. BACKGROUND

There is currently no way to visualize the pathways that students take through majors at the University of Virginia. What courses do students take to complete their degree, and in what order? Are pathways similar or different based

on sociodemographic variables such as gender, race, or first generation or transfer status? Part of the motivation for this comes from the evidence that these groups have different levels of success in the classroom, and their course loads have different levels of difficulty[1]. There is also evidence to support that these factors have an impact on the majors that students choose [2]. Answering these questions would be a great benefit to both the students and faculty here at UVA. With this information, students will be able to make more informed choices about when and what classes to take to fulfill their major requirements. Departments would be able to better understand their course offering and structure classes and curriculum to better support the students in their department.

Students Per Major

Fig. 1. Distribution of Students per Major

Prior to working with us, the UVA CTE had done a lot of work looking at differences in socioeconomic groups at

the University of Virginia. So they had the resources and experience to display the information and the vision of what they wanted the course progression to look like. However, they didn't have the data handling expertise to turn the ten years of course data they were sitting on into the pathways that they wanted.

IV. DATA

For our data we had 13 datasets (csv files), one for each school year starting 2009-2010 through 2021-2022, as well as an additional csv file that has each student with their graduating majors. Each of the 13 datasets has a row for each class that was taken by each student and 27 columns which includes factors important to us such as course, course number, semester taken, and anonymized student id. An issue with this data is that the columns for sociodemographic factors were not allowed to be released to us, so they are all n/a. To get past this we received a list of possible values for these variables so we were able generate fake values of these columns allowing us to create a framework they can use with the full data. Another important note with the data is that the major at graduation is in a separate file so we had to do some joining to get the right people in the right place with the right majors. Finally, we have to keep in mind that not all majors have the same traffic (as seen in Fig 1) so with majors like Economics with over 5,000 students we can get more definitive results than a major like Medieval Studies with 12 students.

Outside of the data that we were given, we have developed a couple of data documents regarding UVA major course requirements. We developed one document with information about every major and the required courses to complete that major (Table I). We also developed a data document about the courses at UVA and the majors that utilize those courses in their requirements (Table II).

TABLE I
MAJOR REQUIREMENT - ECONOMICS

Required Courses	Calc II	Econ Elec
*1 Calc II	MATH 1220	ECON 3030
ECON 2010	MATH 1320	ECON 3040
ECON 2020	APMA 1110	ECON 3050
*4 Econ Elec		ECON 3430

TABLE II
COURSE BY MAJOR - ECON

Major	ECON 2010	ECON 2020	ECON 3010
Commerce	1	1	
Economics	1	1	1
Mathematics			
Public Policy	1		

1 Denotes required class, nothing means not required.

V. METHODS

We created a program in R where all a user need to do is specify the major they would like to analyze and the most

current year of data available. The program then works to read in all of the csv files automatically and performs various functions required to transform the data into a workable format suitable for analysis. The program outputs three distinct deliverables.

The first is a table showing the breakdown of in what semester do students take each class of a major. Each class in the major is a row and each column is a semester, with the percentage of students who took each class in each semester as the data values. The second part of the output is a csv file which has all of the path students have taken through a specified major. The first column is the path with every class is listed in order with an arrow used as a delimiter to show the order the students in this path took their classes to complete this major. A second column in this dataframe is called n and indicates how many students have completed the major following this path. The file will also contain the average gpa for the path, male to female ratio, first generation student ratio, and underrepresented minority ratio. These are all path level variables. The last file outputted is the same information as the second file but at an individual student level instead of aggregate level.

TABLE III
ECON- SEMESTER BREAKDOWN

Course	S1	S2	S3	S4
ECON 2010	52%	15%	27%	4%
ECON 2020	3%	52%	14%	24%
ECON 3110	10%	0%	74%	0%
MATH 1320	38%	30%	16%	12%
STAT 2120	19%	24%	27%	19%

A big data issue that we had to tackle was finding all of the required courses for each major and finding a good way to format these courses and be able to access it within our programming. This was a tedious process requiring going to each programs website and copying over every course that could count as a major requirement. The outcome of this process was two separate files with the list of majors. The first was a single sheet excel file with a column for each major and a row for every course that could be counted as a major requirement. This file was meant strictly for R use so that we could easily filter only classes used for major to get the paths. The other was a separate excel file with a different sheet for each major. These sheets were a more comprehensive view of each major with a column for the required courses and required electives. The required elective rows had a link to other columns in the major specific sheet with the options to fulfill that elective. The point of this is to was to centralize the major requirements instead of having to go to each department website to find the information.

Another issue we had to tackle was how to deal with both double majors and prerequisite classes. Double majors were an issue because students often took related majors, such as chemistry and physics, where certain classes were options to fulfill requirements in both majors. This meant that

many students had very unique paths through a major because of the quantity of classes, within the major options, above the required amount taken. To deal with this, we added a feature that was called "major only". If "YES", this would make it so we only considered courses directly listed under the department. For the chemistry example, this meant we only looked at courses listed as CHEM in UVA SIS (Student Information System). This raises the number of students who have taken the same courses in the same order, as it shrinks the pool of available options. An important note here is that we did this in a way where students in the dataset still keep their double major status. We felt there was so much we could look into with regard to comparing double majors to single majors or how different sociodemographic factors effect these decisions. For example, first generation college students are less likely to double major[3].

A question that arose during the course of the project was how to handle students who took classes in the same semester. When creating a path of the order they took each class, how should these classes be arranged? What we decided to do was to go by listing order. A class with a lower course number would be first followed by the next highest and so on. However, we added an option to our program to allow for analysis taking into account if classes were taken during the same semester. The path outputted if this option was enabled would look the same as before with an arrow delimiter but with commas between classes taken at the same time. Students would have had to have taken the classes both in the same order and at the same time if multiple major classes were taken during the same semester to be considered as having taken the same path through the major.

TABLE IV
EXAMPLE CHEMISTRY PATH BREAKDOWN

Path	n
CHEM 1410→ CHEM 1411→ CHEM 1420	287
CHEM 1810→ CHEM 1811→ CHEM 1820	149
CHEM 2410→ CHEM 2411→ CHEM 2420	98

Table IV is an example of what one of the R program outputs would look like. The first columns is a list of paths students have taken through a certain major. The examples in the table have been shortened to fit in the table for this report. The second column is a count of how many students have followed that exact path through the major. Not included in this table but included in the real output are summary statistic columns such as gpa, gender ratio, first generation student ratio and more. These statistics are averages taken on the students for each path in the table.

VI. RESULTS

Because of the nature of our task, success for us was defined by creating the deliverables requested by the UVA Center for Teaching Excellence. We have been using anonymized data with no access to real values for variables such as gpa, gender ratio, first generation status, etc. However, we created what we

feel are some great tools UVA will be able to use for years to come to analyze problems relating to our work. Our R program is future proofed where UVA will be able to add data every year and run the summary statistics for each major. One thing we did get to create and observe the results of was a semester breakdown of each class. This table showed a percentage of how many students take each class in that semester of college. For a class like intro chemistry for example, most students take it in their first semester here. However, a large percentage will wait until their third semester. The UVA Center for Teaching Excellence will be able to examine each of these paths and see if there lies any differences in student performance. Using that information, they could better recommend to students when to take intro chemistry or make recommendations to the chemistry department on how to structure courses to help with student success.

VII. DISCUSSION

While it is unfortunate we were unable to be apart of the analysis, this was a very important problem we were working on and we have hopefully set it up so that the University can complete the analysis. Any differences in college performance relating to sociodemographic characteristics need to be rooted out and eliminated. We were still able to do a lot with the data we were given however having no grade or sociodemographic data put a limitation on what we could do. There were great examples of predicting future majors and major retention based on grade data [4] and that would have been a great insight to provide.

Our work will be crucial in the discovery of any potential issues with how departments have their major set up. It will also help students make more informed decisions about the classes they are taking, especially when they are first coming into UVA and exploring future disciplines.

VIII. FUTURE WORK

The UVA Center for Teaching Excellence will be continuing our work directly, implementing what we made with the real data and performing analysis. Although there is nothing else that the UVA CTE is stressing right now, there have been plenty of discussions about next steps about what to do with their transformed data. For example, using the data document we created that looks at the individual courses, the CTE would like to see what courses are utilized across the most degree programs. This would help with knowing to offer more sections of this class or increase section size.

Another question that was talked a lot about is extending the research to all courses at UVA, not focusing on major specific issues. For example, looking at things such as switching majors, or if taking a popular course like Calculus or Intro Computer Science raises your GPA if you take it later in your college career as opposed to taking it in your first or second semester. Now that the CTE has access to the transformed data, they are constantly coming up with new ideas on what to do with it, so hopefully they bring out new helpful information to share with teachers, students, and the university.

ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

We would like to thank our advisor and peers at the University of Virginia that helped guide us along the way. We would also like to thank the University of Virginia Center for Teaching Excellence for the support and feedback provided to us the past year.

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